

POLAC JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES (PJSMS)

Vol. 3 No. 1 March, 2025

ISSN - Print: 2992-5009; Online: 2437-1246

Editor-in-Chief

Solomon Olubunmi, PhD

Editor

Samson Olowo Kolawole, PhD

Associate Editors

Vincent Okwudili Iweama, PhD

Nwachi Loveday Agwu, PhD

Ayogu Chiagolum Elochukwu

Shamsudeen Alhassan Musa

Sagir Lawal, PhD

Vahyala Adamu Tari, PhD

Ubong Evans Abraham, PhD

Kabiru Umar, PhD

Valentine Ayo Mebu, PhD

Ajene Sunday Apeh, PhD

Editorial Advisory Board

Prof. Benjamin Oladapo Olley,

Prof. Benjamin Oluwabunmi Omolayo

Prof. Mike Duru,

Prof. Abdullahi Hassan Gorondutse,

Prof. Hussaini Tukur Hassan,

Prof. Junaidu Muhammad Kurawa

Prof. Canice Esidene Erunke,

Prof. Ahmad Audu Maiyaki,

Prof. Zubairu Kwambo Dagona,

Prof. Abu Maji,

Dr Bello Halilu Rogo,

Dr Abdulrazaq Ibrahim

Prediction of Psychological Well-Being Based on Self-Differentiation Among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets

Ibrahim Arobo Dauda & Hassan Salawu Abu

Department of Psychology,
Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano.

E-mail: ibdrobo2007@yahoo.com; +234737833794

Abstract

Psychological well-being supports mental health. Stress negatively relates to psychological well-being, but no study of these variables was found to target stress stress-vulnerable population as cadets. This study investigated the prediction of self-differentiation on psychological well-being among cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy, whose training made them vulnerable to stress. The theory of psychological well-being provided the framework. Expos-factor method, cross-sectional design and convenient sampling technique were utilized. The study sampled 563 cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy from all the faculties and departments of the academy. The investigation revealed that self-differentiation is a significant predictor of psychological well-being among the cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy $F(4, 558) = 22.524, p < 0.05$. Emotional cut off is a positive and significant predictor of psychological well-being ($\beta = .092, t = 2.171, p < 0.05$). Fusion with others is a positive and significant predictor of psychological well-being ($\beta = .178, t = 3.555, p < 0.05$). I-position is a significantly positive predictor of psychological well-being among cadets ($\beta = .366, t = 8.841, p < 0.05$). Emotional reactivity is an insignificant predictor of psychological well-being ($\beta = .028, t = .567, p > 0.05$). Self-differentiation is a significant predictor of psychological well-being. The higher the emotional cutoff, the higher the psychological well-being. The higher the fusion with others, the higher the psychological well-being. The greater the I position, the greater the psychological well-being. Further study should investigate how self-differentiation could be used to enhance psychological well-being. Clinicians should take note of self-differentiation and its levels when conducting psychological well-being assessment or evaluation, especially among Nigeria Police cadets and similar populations.

Keywords: Cadets, Nigeria Police Academy, Psychological Well-Being, Self-differentiation.

Article history:

Received: 17 January 2025

Reviewed: 20 February 2025

Accepted: 29 March 2025

About the Journal: PJSMS is a multidisciplinary journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil-Kano, Nigeria, published biannually.

Dauda, I. A. & Abu, H. S. (2025).

Prediction of Psychological Well-Being Based on Self-Differentiation Among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets

Introduction

The practice of mental health professionals over the years has revolved around mental illness, its assessment, diagnosis and treatment. This narrowed focus has prevented practitioners and researchers from investigating other variables that could be associated with mental health, which can be used to sustain or improve mental health, in other words, prevent mental illness. Increasing evidence has supported a causal relationship between greater psychological well-being and better overall health and improved disease-specific outcomes (Ong, 2010; DeSteno, Gross & Kubzansky, 2013; Cohen, Bavishi & Rozanski, 2016). The realization that psychological well-being is associated with mental health necessitates further investigation of variables that could predict psychological well-being. The variable(s) that is/are eventually found to relate to psychological well-being could be used to enhance psychological well-being, which supports mental health. Consequently, increasing mental health among the populace in line with global advocacy can be profoundly supported. Changing states of well-being by increasing positive emotion and decreasing negative emotion result in salutary physiological/biological changes (e.g., inflammation, immune functioning), and contribute to diverse positive health outcomes, e.g., cardiovascular health (Feller et al., 2018).

Cadets, the target population and Adolescents are suitable for a timely preventive solution because they are vulnerable. Many mental disorders, including emotional and behavioural difficulties and adjustment problems, have their roots in adolescence ages which often go undiagnosed and untreated for years (Desouky, Abdellatif & Salah, 2015;

Stromback, Malmgren-Olsson & Wiklund, 2013). Their engagement is characterized by stress. The capacity and skills to cope with these stressors are significantly associated with their psychological well-being (Seiffge-Krenke & Krick, 2015). Considering these, several efforts are recorded in looking for solutions to promote mental health, especially among the mentally ill most vulnerable population.

In furtherance of the noble desire to enhance psychological well-being among vulnerable persons, a study confirmed the validity and the reliability of the differentiation of self-inventory short form (DSI-SF) among the population and concluded that it is a valid and reliable measure of self-differentiation among Nigeria Police cadets (Dauda, Karick & Dagona, 2023). Also, in the same purpose, a relevant confirmatory analysis of the religious life and orientation scale revealed significant, valid and reliable evidence for the construct among Nigeria police academy cadets (Dauda, Karick, Kolawole, Abdulkareem, & Dagona, 2021). Valid and reliable evidence motivated an investigation which reported that intrinsic religious orientation does not significantly predict psychological wellbeing, but extrinsic and quest religious orientation significantly predicted psychological wellbeing among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets (Dauda, Zumlong & Haa 2021).

Psychological well-being is synonymous with mental health; it enables people, including cadets, to function optimally in all engagements. Stress influences psychological well-being to thrive. Enhancing psychological well-being would promote and sustain the optimal function of cadets in training, and beyond its usefulness could also be extended to a similar population. Huppert (2009)

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

reported a strong possibility that by increasing flourishing (psychological well-being) in the population, we might do more to reduce common mental and behavioural problems than by focusing exclusively on the treatment of disorder. Therefore, understanding variables that predict psychological well-being can be utilized to enhance cadets' efficient functioning. Mental illness is prevalent; its assessment, diagnosis and treatment can be supplemented by a preventive approach. Promoting psychological well-being among the populace is capable of fortifying or improving mental health, which is the desire of the global advocacy for mental health promotion.

The objective of the study is to uncover the predictive ability of self-differentiation on psychological well-being among Nigeria Police cadets; to find out the predictive capacity of self-differentiation's levels (Emotional Reactivity, Emotional Cut off, I-Position and Fusion with others) on psychological well-being among Nigeria Police cadets. The significance of the study would unravel the prediction of self-differentiation and its levels on psychological well-being among Nigeria Police cadets. Clinicians can also decide suitable assessment, intervention, evaluation of intervention and referral that can address psychological well-being-related issues. Researchers can take advantage of the knowledge to plan how findings can be knit into psychological well-being enhancement training to empower individuals with internal capacity or resources to function at their best.

Empirical examination of psychological well-being theory, which provided the frame for this study, was possible due to the development of a valid and adequate measurement of self-differentiation, such as DSI (Differentiation of Self Inventory, Skowron & Schmitt, 2003). Psychological

well-being theory argued that whether or not a person has a positive attitude toward self or life, self-acceptance was a central to psychological well-being (Jahoda, 1958). The theory holds that regardless of people's attitude toward a self-accepted person, the self-acceptance remains unchanged. This is similar to the I-Position level of self-differentiation as described by Bowen (1985), that individuals tend to remain pretty calm even under stress, no matter what happens in life, they know they will never lose sense of who they are. There is no point getting upset about things they cannot change; fairly self-accepting, self-esteem rarely depends on how others think of them; they tend to feel pretty stable under stress. Unlike with psychological well-being, where approval from others isn't required to accept self, fusion with others is a level of measuring self-differentiation that reflects that the individual usually needs a lot of encouragement from others when starting a big job or task. They feel a need for approval from virtually everyone in their life. Often, they agree with others just to appease them and feel unsure when others are not around to help them make a decision (Bowen, 1976).

Psychological well-being theory argues that the ability to achieve warm, trusting interpersonal relationships, which are central to overall psychological well-being, is paramount (Maslow, 1968). But when a warm relationship is formed, Emotional Cut off, a level of self-differentiation measurement described by Bowen (1976), showed individuals tend to feel uncomfortable and distance self when people get too close to them. When a relationship becomes very intense, the urge to run away sets in. Psychological well-being theory revolves around warm relationships with one another. Individual with a high level of differentiation maintain their closeness to others (Hainlen, Jankowski, Paine & Sandage, 2016). Bowen's family system model emphasizes the strong

positive relationship of self-differentiation with psychological well-being (Kerr & Bowen, 1988). In their study, Skowron, Stanley and Shapiro (2008) posited that levels of self-differentiation are related to psychological well-being.

Literature Review

Self-differentiation might influence psychological well-being, as it enables individuals to maintain healthy relational functioning, competence in problem solving, less disposed to psychological challenges in relation to various aspects of psychological well-being, such as improved self-esteem and interpersonal capacity (Bowen, 1978). A significant correlation between normative identity style, self-differentiation and psychological well-being exists (Ghader & Moradi, 2018). Fusion and emotional reactivity, aspects of self-differentiation, mediate the relationship between interdependent self-construal and psychological well-being among US college students (Ross & Murdock, 2014). Self-differentiation positively predicted psychological well-being (La, 2018). There is a significant positive relationship between self-differentiation and psychological health, and a significant negative relationship between self-differentiation and 3 subscales of psychological health that are physical signs, anxiety, depression signs and a positive and significant relationship between social function and self-differentiation (Sohrabia, Asadib, Habibollahzadec & PanaAlid 2013). The main levels of all components of self-differentiation were greater for European Americans than for Koreans; self-differentiation was associated with psychological well-being more strongly in American samples than in Korean counterparts (Chung & Gale, 2006). Self-differentiation predicted lower psychological

well-being after controlling for distress levels (Skowron et al, 2008).

Studies on self-differentiation, its levels and psychological well-being were reported alongside other variables such as family, normative and informative identity style, conflict, self-efficacy, need fulfilment, marital relationships, gender, culture, psychological health, defense mechanism, self-construal, and cognition. Self-differentiation and psychological well-being studies cut across gender, age, educational levels and race. There are a few studies reported on self-differentiation and its levels on psychological well-being for the scientific community and researchers to utilize. These suggest the need for more studies on the variable (self-differentiation) and its levels on psychological well-being across different populations to illuminate relationships, differences or influence, etc. From available studies reviewed, it is obvious that almost all the studies on self-differentiation and psychological well-being were carried out outside Nigeria, and none targeted police cadets or investigated the prediction of self-differentiation's levels on psychological well-being. The entire review of literature revealed that few studies investigated the prediction of levels of self-differentiation on psychological well-being.

Two hypotheses were generated: 1. Self-differentiation would significantly predict psychological well-being among Nigeria Police cadets. 2. Self-differentiation's levels (Emotional Reactivity, Emotional Cut off, I-Position and Fusion with others) would significantly predict psychological well-being among Nigeria Police Cadets.

Methods

Since the number of the target population is known as 2080 Cadets, at a 95% level of confidence interval and 3.5% margin of error, the sample size was determined using the

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

sample size determination table (Research advisors, 2006). The table recommends a minimum of 563 samples. The participants included 400 (71%) male and 163 (29%) female cadets, 351 (62.2%) were Christian, 208 (36.9%) Muslim, from four faculties across the 17 departments (One hundred, two hundred, three hundred, four hundred and five hundred levels) of the Nigeria Police Academy. Participation in the study was completely voluntary and void of harm.

A multiple regression design was used. The independent variables (although not manipulated) in this study are: self-differentiation and its levels. Although self-differentiation has four levels (emotional reactivity, emotional cutoff, I-Position and fusion with others), both the construct and the levels' predictions were examined. The dependent variable is psychological well-being. It has six levels (autonomy, environmental mastery, personal relation with others, personal growth, self-acceptance and purpose in life). But the study measured the prediction of self-differentiation on only the total psychological well-being. The study is premised on a positivist philosophical assumption; it is chosen as the preferred worldview for research, which tries to interpret observations in terms of facts or measurable entities (Fadhel, 2002).

Differentiation of self-inventory short form (DSI-SF) (Drake, Murdock, Marszalek, & Barber, 2015). The DSI-SF consist of 20 items. The 20 items are divided into four subscales: emotional cut off (EC), emotional reactivity (ER), fusion with others (FO) and I-position (IP). Some of the sample items include: I'm overly sensitive to criticism, and I'm fairly self-accepting. Participants rate each item on a 6-point Likert scale: 1=Not at all characteristic of me. 2=Slightly characteristic of me. 3=Moderately characteristic of me. 4=More characteristic of

me. 5=Very characteristic of me. 6=Extremely characteristic of me, where higher values indicate more differentiation of self. The DSI-SF has been used as a measurement of a person's overall differentiation of self. Scoring: The number of items for each subscale is as follows: EC=4,7, and 15; ER=6,9,11,14, 16 and 18; FO=2,5,8,13, and 17; IP=1,3,10,12,19 and 20. As with the DSI-R (Skworon & Schmitt, 2003), several of the items in the DSI-SF are reverse scored (i.e. a 6=1, 5=2, 4=3, etc). The following items are reverse score: EC=4,7, and 15; ER=6,9,11,14, and 16; FO=2,5,8,13 and 17; and IP=20. To calculate a subscale score, take the average of all items within a subscale (i.e. average of 1+2+3). For the total scale, like with the subscales, the average of the scales is taken (i.e., average of EC1+EC2+EC3).

Short measurement of psychological well-being (SMPWB) (Clarke, Marshall, Ryff & Wheaton, 2001). The SMPWB instrument is a self-report short version, 18 items, 3 for each of its six constructs: 1. environmental mastery, 2. autonomy, 3. positive relations with others, 4. personal growth, 5. purpose in life and 6. self-acceptance. Like Ryff's (1989a) short measure of psychological well-being, it responded to between 3 and 5 minutes. Items are rated on a seven-point Likert scale. 1= strongly agree; 2= somewhat agree; 3 = a little agree; 4 = neither agree nor disagree; 5 = a little disagree; 6=somewhat disagree; 7 = strongly disagree. The scale is regarded as the best objective measure of psychological well-being (Conway & Macleod, 2002) and has received extensive cross-cultural validation (Staudinger, Baltes & Fleeson, 1999). Its validity and reliability were extensively measured and accepted in a study by Sirigatti et al. (2009).

Scoring: The autonomy subscale items' numbers are 15, 17, and 18. The

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

environmental mastery subscale items' numbers are 4, 8, and 9. The personal growth subscale items' numbers are 11, 12, and 14. The positive relations with others subscale items' numbers are 6, 13, and 16. The purpose in life subscale items' numbers are 3, 7, and 10. The self-acceptance subscale items' numbers are 1, 2, and 5. The following item numbers are reverse-score: 4, 5, 6, 15 and 16. Reverse-scored items are worded in the opposite direction of what the scale is measuring. The formula for reverse-scoring an item is: $((\text{number of scale points}) + 1) - (\text{respondent's answer})$. For example, item 1 is a 7-point scale. If a respondent answered 3 on Q1, re-code their answer as: $(7+1) - 3 = 5$. In other words, enter a 5 for this respondent's answer to item 1. To calculate subscale scores for each participant, sum the respondents' scores for each subscale's items; higher scores mean levels of psychological well-being. The combined scores can also provide an overall well-being total. Higher values for the whole scale correspond to higher levels of well-being, the values ranging between 18 and 126. Above-average of each subscale and the total score indicate psychological well-being.

A convenient sampling technique was used in this study; the available cadets were approached in their respective departments at each level, and they were requested to volunteer and participate in the study. Only those who volunteered to participate were considered for the data collection procedure. The permission to administer the questionnaires was sought, and approval was granted from the appropriate authority of the target institution (Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil). The collection of data was assisted by two psychologists, who were instructed on how to administer, guide participants where necessary and collect the questionnaires after being responded to accordingly. They were thoroughly instructed to read and carefully explain the expectations of the study to

participants at various levels across the academic departments in the academy.

The questionnaire consists of a consent page is the front, which briefly explains the purpose of the study, procedure, potential harm, risk or discomfort, right to refusal or withdrawal, confidentiality and statement of consent. Participants were requested to read through it and familiarize themselves with their expectations in the research conduct. Those who consented to participate continued with the filling of the questionnaire. Ethical considerations ensured the condition of participation in the study was entirely harmless and voluntary (it is inscribed on the questionnaires). Confidentiality is protected as only the initials of respondents are required during their response to the questionnaires. Data was used and analyzed for research purposes, in a manner that individual identity was not revealed. Participants responded to each item of the instruments as applied to them. Participants were encouraged to respond to all the items in the instruments, as no response within the provided scales is wrong. A brief instruction and awareness of the expectations of the respondents are highlighted. The questionnaire was divided into sections A-D, which included biodata, differentiation of the self-inventory short form, and a measure of psychological well-being. The statistic package for social science version 21 (SPSS version 21) was used to perform: First, descriptive analyses were used to describe the participants' characteristics. Finally, the multiple regression analysis was used to test the generated hypotheses.

Results**Table 1**

Model Summary of Self-differentiation on Psychological Well-being

R	R Square
.373 ^a	.139

a. Predictors: (Constant), I - Position, Emotional Reactivity, Emotional Cutoff, Fusion With Others

b. Dependent Variable: Psychological Wellbeing

Table 2

ANOVA summary: Self-differentiation and Psychological Well-being

Model		Sum of Squares	of Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	12947.391	4	3236.848	22.524	.000 ^b
1	Residual	80187.060	558	143.704		
	Total	93134.451	562			

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Wellbeing

b. Predictors: (Constant), I - Position, Emotional Reactivity, Emotional Cutoff, Fusion With Others

Table 3

Regression Coefficients Summary of Self-differentiation and its Levels and Psychological Well-being

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	
	B	Std. Error
(Constant)	44.848	4.405
Emotional Cutoff	.318	.147
1 Emotional Reactivity	.076	.135
Fusion With Others	.442	.124
I - Position	1.127	.128

a. Dependent Variable: Psychological Wellbeing

Discussions

Both the explained model and variance indicated that self-differentiation significantly predicted psychological well-being among cadets of the Nigeria Police Academy. This result was supported by Bohlander (1999); Chung & Gale (2006); Sohrabia et al. (2013); La (2018), and Tarkhan (2018), in their investigation to uncover self-differentiation prediction on psychological well-being among other populations. The cadets could clearly define themselves, their beliefs, control themselves and navigate life, and rationally decide in most problematic situations in which most people show unintentional behaviour and make illogical decisions. This predicted their ability to see and accept strengths and weaknesses, have meaning in life, grow potentials to reality, have close valuable ties with others, set and manage daily issues of life, follow personal principles even if they disagree with social demands and traditions (Diener, Lucas & Oishi, 2002).

The regression coefficients clearly illustrated the independent prediction of the four levels of self-differentiation on psychological well-being. The level of Emotional cut-off made a direct significant prediction of psychological well-being. This result showed that the higher the emotional cutoff, the higher the psychological well-being among the cadets, although the regression coefficient is weak. Emotional reactivity, the other level of self-differentiation, insignificantly predicted psychological well-being. Fusion with others had a direct, significant prediction of psychological well-being. The result showed that the more fusion with others, the greater the psychological well-being of cadets, although the regression coefficient is weak. Finally, the last of the levels of self-differentiation, I-position, had a direct significant prediction of psychological well-being among cadets. The result showed that the more I-position, the greater the psychological well-being of the cadets, although the regression coefficient is weak.

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

Multiple regression uncovers the significance, direction and strength of coefficients between the various levels of self-differentiation on psychological well-being among Cadets. Emotional cutoff positively, significantly predicted psychological well-being among cadets. The result shows that the higher the emotional cutoff, the higher the psychological well-being among the cadets. As tendency to distance self when people get too close and its discomfort culminates in to urge to run away when the relationship becomes very intense. It increases the ability to see and accept strengths and weaknesses, manage daily issues of life to be meaningful, growing potentials into reality. Have close and valuable ties with others, set and follow personal principles even if they disagree with social demands and traditions. The regression coefficient is weak and direct (positive). It means the increase in cadets' emotional cutoff results in an increase in the psychological well-being of the cadets.

Fusion with others positively, significantly predicted psychological well-being among cadets. The results show that the more fusion with others, the more psychological well-being of cadets. The regression coefficient is weak and direct (positive). The more the usually need for lot of encouragement from others when starting a big task, the need for approval from virtually everyone. Often agree with others just to appease them and feel unsure when others are not around to help make a decision. Increases the ability to see and accept strengths and weaknesses, and manage daily issues of life to be meaningful, growing potentials to reality. Have close and valuable ties with others, the ability to set and follow personal principles even if they disagree with social demands and traditions.

I-position positively, significantly predicted psychological well-being among cadets. The results show that the more I-position, the more

the psychological well-being of the cadets. The regression coefficient is weak and direct (positive). The more the cadets' self-identity, acceptance of unchanged happening and stability under stress increase their acceptance of strengths and weaknesses. They manage daily issues of life to be meaningful, growing potentials into reality. They develop the ability to follow their personal principles even if they disagree with social demands and traditions.

Emotional reactivity did not significantly predict psychological well-being among cadets. Although the result was positively insignificant and the coefficient is weak, it could show that the more emotional reactivity, the more psychological well-being of cadets. Increase in best of feelings at times, trouble thinking clearly, feels as if riding an emotional roller-coaster at times, over-sensitive to criticism and argument with partner, doesn't let go easily when upset, very sensitive to being hurt by others. Could increase the ability to see and accept strengths and weaknesses, and manage daily issues of life to be meaningful, growing potentials to reality, have close and valuable ties with others, ability to set and follow personal principles even if they disagree with social demands and traditions. The regression coefficient is weak and direct (positive).

Conclusion

Self-differentiation is a significant predictor of psychological well-being among cadets. It level, Emotional cut-off is a significant predictor of psychological well-being among cadets. The increase in emotional cutoff leads to an increase in the psychological well-being of the cadets. Emotional reactivity is not a significant predictor of psychological well-being among cadets. Fusion with others is a significant predictor of psychological well-being among cadets. The increased fusion with others leads to an increase in the

Print ISSN: 2992-5009

Online ISSN: 2437-1246

psychological well-being of cadets. I-position is a significant predictor of psychological well-being among cadets. The increase in I-position results in an increase in the psychological well-being of the cadets.

Recommendations

Clinicians should consider self-differentiation and its levels in planning psychological well-being enhancement training.

Clinicians should endeavour to consider self-differentiation and its levels in the assessment, intervention and evaluation of interventions of psychological well-being enhancement and sustenance.

References

- Bohlander, W. R. (1999). Differentiation of self, need fulfilment, and psychological well-being in married men. *Psychological Report*, 84(3,2), 1274-1280. Doi:10.2466/PRO.84.3.1274-1280
- Bowen, M. (1976). Theory in the practice of psychotherapy. P. J. Guerin, Jr. (Ed.), *Family therapy: Theory and practice*, 42-90. Garner Press.
- Bowen, M. (1978). *Family Therapy in Clinical Practice*. Northvale, NJ Jason Aronson.
- Bowen, M. (1985). *Family Therapy in Clinical Practice*. Jason Aronson.
- Chung, H. & Gale, J. (2006). Comparing self-differentiation and psychological well-being between Korean and European American students. *Contemporary Family Therapy* 28, 367-381. doi:10.1007/s10591-006-9013-z
- Clarke, P. J., Marshall, V. M., Ryff, C. D., & Wheaton, B. (2001). Measuring psychological well-being in the Canadian study of health and aging. *International Psychogeriatrics* 13, 79-90. doi:10.1017/S1041610202008013.
- Cohen, R., Bavishi, C. & Rozanski, A. (2016). Purpose in life and its relationship to all-cause mortality and cardiovascular events: a meta-analysis. *Psychosomatic Medicine*. 78, 122-133. doi: 10.1097/psy.0000000000000274
- Conway, C., & Macleod, A. (2002). Well-being: It's importance in clinical research. *Clinical Psychology*, 16, 26-29.
- Dauda, A. I., Karick, H. & Dagona, K. Z. (2023). Confirmatory Analysis of Differentiation of Self Inventory Short Form among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets. *EAS J Psychol Behav Sci*; 5(5), 145-150
- Dauda, A. I., Karick, H., Kolawole, O. S., Abdulkareem, B. H. & Dagona, S. S. (2021). Confirmatory Analysis for Religious Life and Orientation Scale among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets. *Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues*, 1(1), 20 -29
- Dauda, A. I., Zumlong, J. D. & Haa, N. T. (2021). Religious Orientation as a Predictor of Psychological Wellbeing among Nigeria Police Academy Cadets. *African Journal for the Psychological Study of Social Issues*, 24(1), 148 -156
- Desouky, D. S, Abdellatif, I. R. & Salah. O. M. (2015). Prevalence and comorbidity of depression, anxiety and obsessive compulsive disorders among Saudi secondary school girls, Taif Area, KSA. *Arch Iran Med* 18: 234-238.
- DeSteno, D., Gross, J. J. & Kubzansky, L. (2013). Affective science and health: the importance of emotion and emotion regulation. *Health Psychology* 32, 474-486. doi: 10.1037/a0030259
- Diener, E., Lucas, R., & Oishi, S. (2002). Subjective well-being: The science of happiness and life satisfaction. In: R. C. Snyder, J. S. Lopez, S. J. (eds): *The Handbook of Positive Psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Drake, J. R., Murdock, N. L., Marszalek, J. M., & Barber, C. E. (2015). Differentiation of self-inventory—short form: development and preliminary validation. *Contemporary Family Therapy*, 37(2), 101-112.

- Fadhel K. (2002). Positivist and hermeneutic paradigm, A critical evaluation under their structure of scientific practice. *The Sosland Journal*, 21-28.
- Feller, S. C., Castillo, E. G., Greenberg, J. M., Abascal, P., Van Horn, R., Wells, K. B. (2018). Emotional well-being and public health: proposal for a model national initiative. *Public Health Rep.* 133, 136–141. doi: 10.1177/0033354918754540
- Ghader, P., & Moradi, F. (2018). The study of the relationship between normative and informative identity styles with differentiation of self and psychological well-being of the students. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development.* 9(4), 106-111.
- Hainlen, R. L., Jankowski, P. J., Paine, D. R., & Sandage, S. J. (2016). Adult attachment and well-being: Dimensions of differentiation of self as mediators. *Contemporary Family Therapy*, 38(2), 172-183
- Huppert, A. F. (2009). Psychological well-being: Evidence regarding its causes and consequences, applied psychology. *Health and Well-Being*, 1(2), 137-164.
- Jahoda, M. (1958). *Current concepts of positive mental health*. Basic Books GREEN.
- Kerr, M., & Bowen, M. (1988). *Family evaluation*. Norton.
- La, S (2018). The impact of generational family conflict, bicultural self-efficacy, and differentiation of self on psychological well-being among Asian American adult. A dissertation submitted to Graduate School in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Philosophy New Mexico State University Las Cruces, New Mexico.
- Maslow, A. H. (1968). *Toward a psychology of being*, ed. 2. Van Nostrand.
- Ong, A. D. (2010). Pathways linking positive emotion and health in later life. *Current Directorate of Psychology Science.* 19, 358–362. doi: 10.1177/0963721410388805
- Research advisor (2006) Sample size table. [http://research-advisors.com/tools/sampleSize .htm](http://research-advisors.com/tools/sampleSize.htm). retrieved 2010/02/05 12:14
- Ross, S. A. & Murdock, L. N. (2014). Differentiation of self and well-being: The moderating effect of self-construal. *Contemporary family therapy*, 36, 485 – 496. Doi:10.1007/s10591-006-9013-z
- Ryff, C. D. (1989a). Beyond Ponce de Leon and life satisfaction: New directions in quest of successful ageing. *International Journal of Behavioural Development*, 12(1), 35-55. doi: 10.1177/016502548901200102
- Seiffge-Krenke, I. & Krick, A. (2015). Health promotion in schools. *International Encyclopedia of the Social Sciences (Second edition)*, 669-673. doi:10.1016/8978-0-08-097086-8.14051-6
- Sirigatti, S., Stefanile, C., Giannetti, E., Iani, L., Penzo, I., & Mazzeschi, A. (2009). Assessment of factor structure of Ryff's psychological well-being scales in Italian adolescents. *Bollettino Di Psicologia Applicata*, 259, 30-50.
- Skowron, A. E., & Schmitt, T. A. (2003). Assessing interpersonal fusion: Reliability and validity of a new DSI fusion with others subscale. *Journal of Marital and Family Therapy*, 29, 209-222. doi: 10.1111/j.1752-0606.2003.tb01201. x.
- Skowron, A. E., Stanley, L. K., & Shapiro, D. M. (2008). A Longitudinal perspective on differentiation of self, interpersonal and psychological well-being in young adulthood. *Contemporary Family Therapy* 31, 3-18. DOI 10.1007/s10591-008-9075-1
- Sohrabia, R., Asadib, M., Habibollahzadec, H., & PanaAlid, A. (2013). Relationship between self-self in Bowen's family therapy and psychological health. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, 1773-1775. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.07.030
- Staudinger, V. M., Baltes, P. B., & Fleeson, W. (1999). Predictors of subjective

physical health and global well-being: Similarities and differences between the United States and Germany. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76, 305-319. doi: [10.1037/0022-3514.76.2.305](https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.76.2.305)

Stromback, M., Malmgren-Olsson, E. & Wiklund, M. (2013). Girls need to strengthen each other as a group': experiences from a gender-sensitive stress management intervention by youth-friendly Swedish health services – a qualitative study. *BMC Public Health*; 13: 907.

Tarkhan, M. (2018). Predicting of psychological well-being through defence mechanisms and cognitive self-differentiation in students. *Social Cognition* 7(2), 130 – 144.